

Mixed Reality Interface for Managing Heterogeneous Robot Teams in Complex Environments

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Abstract—Mixed Reality (MR) interfaces have been widely used for controlling single mobile robots, but their application for managing teams of mobile robots remains an under-explored area. This extended abstract presents preliminary work on HORUS: Holistic Operational Reality for Unified Systems, a Mixed Reality interface designed to manage diverse robot teams, including wheeled, legged, and aerial robots. HORUS enables operators to monitor robot status, view real-time sensor data, and assign tasks to individual robots, subsets of the team, or the entire team via a Mini Map (Ground Station). The system supports teleoperation with bespoke control interfaces tailored to different robot types, ensuring optimal performance for various platforms. While the wheeled robot multi-robot teleoperation functionality has been fully implemented, work is ongoing to integrate multi-task assignments for wheeled robots and then integrate legged robots and drones into the system.

Index Terms—Mixed Reality, Virtual Reality, Robot teams, Teleoperation

I. INTRODUCTION

The field of robotics has seen significant advancements in recent years, particularly in developing heterogeneous robot teams for complex tasks such as disaster response and search and rescue [1]. As these teams become more diverse and capable, there is a growing need for intuitive and efficient interfaces that allow human operators to manage and control multiple robots simultaneously.

MR interfaces have been successfully applied to single robot control scenarios, offering improved situational awareness and intuitive command inputs. For instance, ARviz [2] and iviz [3] have demonstrated the potential of MR interfaces for visualizing sensor data and controlling individual mobile robots. In the realm of aerial robotics, researchers have explored MR interfaces for teleoperation, focusing on improving operator situational awareness and control precision [4] [5].

Despite these advancements, the application of MR interfaces for managing heterogeneous robot teams remains largely underexplored. While some projects have addressed multi-robot systems management with MR, such as the work by Kennel-Maushart et al. [6] on gesture-based interactions for task allocation in robot teams, there is still a significant gap in integrating comprehensive functionalities for managing diverse robot types within a single MR interface.

HORUS (Holistic Operational Reality for Unified Systems) is a novel Mixed Reality (MR) interface designed to address the challenges of managing heterogeneous robot teams. Unlike

previous systems focusing on specific robot types, HORUS aims to provide a comprehensive solution for managing wheeled, legged, and aerial robots within a single interface.

II. METHODOLOGY

Fig. 1. Robot Manager Panel for checking the robot status, sending a task

The Meta Quest 3 was chosen as the primary MR device due to its color passthrough technology, which offers superior immersion compared to optical see-through displays in HoloLens 2 which shows the MR contents as holograms. Another reason for this choice is the field of view of each device, the field of view of Meta Quest 3 is more than double the field of view of HoloLens 2. This choice enables users to seamlessly blend virtual elements with the real environment, enhancing situational awareness during robot operations and it also gives the possibility to enter full immersion during teleoperation. The robot team currently consists of ROSbots (wheeled robots), with plans to integrate Spot (legged robot) and various drone models (aerial robots) in future iterations. This diverse set of robots allows for comprehensive testing and development of the interface across different robot types. The HORUS Application is developed using Unity, leveraging Meta Quest SDK to take full advantage of the headset's features. ROS (Robot Operating System) serves as the backbone for robot communication and control, for this, the Unity TCP Connector Package was used to create subscribers and publishers to communicate with the robot team through ROS Messages.

HORUS provides a comprehensive Mini Map interface with multiple interaction modes. Operators can monitor robot status, checking individual properties, battery levels, and current task status. The interface allows real-time visualization of sensor data, including camera feeds projected from various perspectives, lidar scans, and other sensor outputs. Task assignment is flexible, enabling operators to allocate tasks to single robots, subgroups, or the entire team directly from the Mini Map. For more direct control, operators can initiate teleoperation for any selected robot.

Fig. 2. Teleoperating with SemiImmersive Wheeled robot teleoperator

Teleoperation in HORUS is available in three modes, Mini Map Control; High-level navigation commands sent via the overhead view, Semi-immersive; A large virtual screen displays the robot’s camera feed and sensor data, allowing for more detailed control, Full immersion; The operator’s view is fully replaced by the robot’s perspective, ideal for precise inspection tasks.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 3. The System Architecture for HORUS Application Experiments

The HORUS system architecture is designed for seamless communication between the MR interface and the heterogeneous robot team. Key components include:

ROS Master: Connects all robots on a common network, facilitating data sharing and synchronized communication. **HORUS Bridge:** A custom ROS node that manages multi-robot task allocation and interactions between the HORUS

app and individual robots. **ROS-Unity Bridge:** Utilizes the `ros_tcp_endpoint` package for TCP-based communication between ROS and Unity. **HORUS Application:** Compiled directly onto the Meta Quest 3, allowing for untethered operation and reduced latency.

This architecture enables real-time data exchange and control between the operator and the robot team, supporting various visualization and interaction modes.

IV. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

The current implementation of HORUS shows promising results in managing wheeled robots, however, several challenges and opportunities for improvement remain. Future work will focus on integrating legged and aerial robots and adapting the interface to support diverse locomotion types and control schemes. Multi-operator support is another key area, aiming to enable collaborative control and shared situational awareness among multiple users. The incorporation of Multi-Modal Large Language Models for AI-assisted decision-making is planned to suggest optimal task allocations and robot configurations. Enhanced data fusion capabilities will improve the integration and visualization of data from multiple robot sensors, creating a more comprehensive environmental understanding. Finally, thorough user studies will be conducted to assess the system’s usability, effectiveness, and impact on operator cognitive load. These advancements will expand HORUS’s capabilities to support more complex, multi-robot operations in various real-world scenarios.

V. CONCLUSION

HORUS is a Mixed Reality interface designed to manage heterogeneous robot teams, currently focusing on wheeled robots with plans to integrate legged and aerial platforms. By offering intuitive visualization and control methods, HORUS aims to simplify the complex task of managing diverse robot teams. While the current implementation shows promise in wheeled robot management, significant work remains to fully realize the system’s goals. Future development will focus on expanding robot-type support, improving multi-robot coordination, and conducting user studies to validate the interface’s effectiveness.

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